

Single- and Multi-Connectivity for Multi-Satellite 6G Communication Networks

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Abstract

This study explores the connectivity strategies for downlink multi-satellites in 6G communication networks. We begin with concepts, technologies, and trade-offs of Single-Connectivity (SC) and Multi-Connectivity (MC). Within the realm of MC, we present three different scenarios, one of which serves as a case study with a particular emphasis on Dual Connectivity (DC). This DC is performed between Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO) and Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites for public safety systems. To improve reliability, we consider packet duplication mechanisms in addition to multi-band satellite capabilities. This supports the LEO link, addresses its limited availability, and facilitates a smooth handover between LEO satellites. Using link-level simulation, outage probability is examined by comparing the SC and MC modes under normal and adverse weather conditions. The findings of this study pave the way for more research to enhance connectivity solutions for more reliable and efficient global communication networks by bringing to light the MC opportunities for multi-satellite systems.

1 Introduction

The Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) has received a lot of attention, especially with the need for ubiquitous, high-speed internet connectivity. In contrast to the Terrestrial Network (TN), NTN offers global coverage without being constrained by geographical limits, weather conditions, or mobility concerns. Recognizing its potential, 3GPP has begun the standardization process with the study's report in Release 15 [1], followed by solutions for 5G New Radio (NR) in Release 16 [2]. The NTN was then included for the first time in mobile communication standards with Release 17 [3]. Releases 18 and 19 will further enhance the functionalities by addressing more features such as the coverage for handheld devices and enabling regenerative payloads.

Developing connectivity aspects is critical to facilitate TN-NTN efficient integration and make use of multi-link connections provided by different layers (i.e., space, air, and ground). The NTN consists of multi-satellites in various orbits (Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO), Medium Earth Orbit (MEO), and Low Earth Orbit (LEO)), as well as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). As a result, the User Equipment (UE) could receive multiple signals from several nodes at the same time, which is known as the Multi-Connectivity (MC) case. It is also possible to be connected to a single node and move

between nodes sequentially, which is known as Single Connectivity (SC). MC in TN has been standardized [4] and has sparked widespread research interest [5]. On the other hand, it is a candidate for NTN Release 19 and was first discussed in [2] with several architecture options for the Next Generation-Radio Access Network (NG-RAN).

From the architectural perspective, the MC is considered when the UE is linked to two or more NTN nodes or a combination of TN and NTN nodes. The NTN NG-RAN could be transparent or regenerative. Full or partial Next Generation NodeB (gNB) functionality can be implemented at the NTN regenerative based on the selected Centralized Unit/Distributed Unit (CU/DU) functional split option [6]. As MC enabler technologies, 3GPP identifies various methods on different layers [5]. Among them, the most relevant are coordinated multi-point /multi-transmission points on the physical layer, Carrier Aggregation (CA) on the medium access control layer, and Dual Connectivity (DC) on the Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) layer.

Despite its widespread study and deployment in TN, MC technologies are still in the early stages of research for satellite systems, receiving little consideration so far. The researchers from the 5G-ALLSTAR project in [7, 8] studied the MC for the case of integrating TN and NTN. For CA, the CADSAT project observed the necessity to extend CA to satellite systems [9-14]. In [15-17], the DYNSTAR project focuses on the DC implementation in the Radio Resource Control (RRC) and PDCP layers for the control and user plane respectively. Recently, the TRANTOR project [18] was launched with one of the primary objectives being to develop the satellite UE as well as gNB to support MC. This project examines a Multi-Satellite configuration with dual-band (Ku and Ka) capabilities, with the satellites deployed either in the same or different Orbits. This configuration is referred to as the M-SBO system in this context.

The downlink of an M-SBO system is the focus of this research. It is motivated by a review of the NTN literature and the realization of the importance of exploring and characterizing potential connectivity strategies. Studying the SC and MC configurations and their trade-offs for M-SBO is a critical foundation for future multi-satellite research. Furthermore, with the various proposed NTN use cases in the literature, there is a need to introduce scenarios and use cases that are suitable for applying MC configurations and selecting the most appropriate MC technology (i.e., CA, DC, etc.) as well as the packet operations (i.e., packet split or duplication). As a result, the goal of this study is to address the issues raised

above by first providing a brief background on SC and MC for M-SBO systems and discussing their trade-offs. Following that, various MC potential scenarios are introduced, with one serving as a case study for a public safety system. The case study investigates the MC capability via DC between GEO (Ku-band) and LEO (Ka-band) satellites. This configuration is considered here to address the problem of limited availability of the LEO link, with the GEO serving as a master node handling control and data signaling. Furthermore, the reliability requirement is prioritized when selecting a public safety use case. As a result, packet duplication is used in conjunction with DC, as well as different propagation characteristics of the bands, as a strategy to improve reliability. This requirement is numerically measured by examining the SC and MC performances under normal and worst-case weather conditions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: The next section discusses SC and MC concepts, technologies, and trade-offs. Section 3 presents potential MC scenarios. Section 4 describes the numerical results, followed by the conclusion in Section 5.

2. Single- and Multi-Connectivity for M-SBO Systems

2.1 Conceptual Overview

In the SC mode, the UE has a single communication link with one satellite. As shown in Fig. 1, there is a single connection between one satellite and the first user (UE1). In some cases, particularly in areas with limited coverage by TN nodes, only one NTN terminal may be connected to meet connectivity requirements. In contrast to MC, which requires additional signaling, the SC procedure between the transmitter and receiver is thus standard and straightforward.

On the other hand, in the case of MC, the UE receives multiple signals simultaneously from multiple satellites. MC can occur also when the UE is linked to the same satellite via multiple carriers in the same or different bands. One node/carrier serves as the Master Node/Primary Component Carrier (MN/PCC), while the other serves as the Secondary Node/Secondary Component Carrier (SN/SCCs). As an example, UE2 is linked to two satellites at the same time in Fig. 1. MC technology gained popularity during the 4G era, and its significance continues to grow in the context of 5G and beyond, particularly in heterogeneous TN and NTN. This interest is justified by its numerous fundamental advantages and ability to meet a wide range of system requirements.

It's worth mentioning here that the primary challenge with SC arises during the handover phase when mobility management is required due to either the user's mobility or the inherent motion of the satellite (in the case of the LEO terminal) [2, 6]. As a result, the handover may be classified into three categories:

- Intra-satellite handover: This handover takes place inside the same satellite. It might happen between satellite bands or beams. The switch-between-bands strategy may be useful when the signal strength varies greatly (as in an emergency communication use case). As a result, switching between bands may be done to take advantage of each one's unique

propagation properties or to deal with traffic load changes. The second intra-satellite handover might occur between the beams, however, due to the quick movement of beam imprints on Earth's surface, exchanges between beams are frequent.

- Inter-satellite handover: This occurs between two satellites in either the same or separate orbits. It could be between two LEOs due to the limited coverage. Furthermore, due to the user's mobility, a handover between two LEOs or between LEO and GEO satellites may occur.
- Inter-Access handover: This occurs between TN and NTN.

The handover concept has primarily been studied in the literature for LEO constellations to deal with their inherent fast mobility around the Earth. The challenge is to develop handover algorithms that ensure a smooth transition with no harmful interruptions. Given the variety of orbits and bands, developing seamless M-SBO handover algorithms is critical.

Fig. 1 Prototype scenario for SC and MC.

2.2 MC Enabler Technologies

The CA and DC techniques that have been standardized by 3GPP for TNs are two potential MC technologies for M-SBO systems, and their underlying principles are briefly described here.

2.2.1 Carrier Aggregation (CA): Consider a satellite transmitting from multiple frequencies in the same or different bands. CA allows exploiting these frequencies to simultaneously transmit multiple signals to the UE, which will aggregate them to increase the data rate and enhance both user and overall network performance. Each aggregated carrier is referred to as a component carrier. It is further subdivided into two subtypes: PCC and SCC. Whereas the PCC is always active, the SCC's status may alternate between inactive and active as required. The SCC is activated, for example when the user requires greater data transmission rates. The PCC, on the other hand, will be accessible continuously and transmit control signals or both control and user data. Depending on its Timing Advance Group (TAG) capabilities, the UE can receive or transmit on one or more component carriers from different cells at the same time. The cells in a single TAG share the same TAG, but in a multiple TAG, the cells have different TAGs.

For the M-SBO systems, the CA can simultaneously exploit the different propagation characteristics of different bands such as the considered Ku and Ka bands. CA is typically divided into three primary types. Intra-band contiguous, intra-band non-contiguous, and inter-band. The former two schemes operate within the same frequency band. Alternatively, inter-band CA, combines carriers from different frequency bands, thereby expanding available capacity and enhancing network performance. Hence, operators may boost data throughput across all available frequencies while reducing excessive spectrum utilization.

2.2.2 Dual Connectivity (DC): In DC, the UE is simultaneously connected to one MN and one or multiple SNs. DC is an extension of the functionalities of CA introduced first in 3GPP Release 12 [19] and called Intra-E-UTRA DC. In contrast to the CA, the main objective here is not only the increase of data rate, but to leverage the advantages of MN and SNs to achieve more features such as seamless handover, and higher reliability. In 3GPP Release 15, the Intra-E-UTRA-DC concept was generalized to MR-DC where the UE is communicated with two nodes from multi-radio access technologies (i.e., eNB and gNB) at the same time [20]. Similarly, NR-NR DC when both nodes are gNB. From the radio protocol architecture perspective, the MN serves as a comprehensive provider of connectivity for users, managing both control and user plane connections. In contrast, the SN solely manages the user plane connectivity. The UE has a single radio Resource Control (RRC) state, based on the MN RRC, and a single Control Plane (CP) connection towards the core network. Each radio node has its own RRC entity NR version which can generate packet data units to be sent to the UE. The management of different CP activities, including the establishment and termination of connections and the administration of handovers, falls under the responsibility of the MN. Upon the establishment of the CP, the transmission of user data takes place through the utilization of the user plane, employing the Data Radio Bearer (DRB) mechanism.

Figure 2 depicts the three different DRB types from a UE perspective: the Master Cell Group (MCG) bearer, the Secondary Cell Group (SCG) bearer, and the Split Cell Group Bearer (SCG). These variations aid in the efficient management of control and user plane data transmission. By handling routing and duplication for split bearers, the PDCP layer improves the overall effectiveness of the system [21]. Packet operations such as packet split, packet duplications, and network coding play crucial roles in satisfying various system requirements such as high data rate and reliability [5]. For instance, the multiple paths from different nodes can be utilized to send different packets which assists in increasing the user data rate. Also, conveying the same packet through different paths yields better reliability [22].

2.3 SC versus MC Trade-Off

In general, each SC and MC strategy has advantages and drawbacks that may influence network performance, user experience, and system design. The following are the trade-off variables:

- **Coverage:** If merely one satellite/node is available, SC could offer coverage for a specific area. However, coverage gaps may arise due to the varying channel environment or due to a failed handover process. Alternatively, if there are multiple links available for the UE, MC extends the coverage because the UE will get the signal from multiple sources (satellites /frequency bands).
- **Latency and Handover:** The handover procedure in SC to transition between satellites/nodes may cause delays and interruptions during UE mobility, particularly when the transmission is handled with a single dish antenna. Alternatively, in the case of MC, the connection to numerous satellites/bands allows smooth handovers and reduces the latency by applying different packet schedulers. This promise of MC comes with additional handover complexities required due to the process of SN addition and release. In addition to the handover between MNs and managing the SN transfers.
- **Capacity and Throughput:** MC can boost capacity and throughput by aggregating resources from numerous links. It can manage network traffic and improve overall performance by using many satellites or frequency bands at the same time. SC, on the other hand, may be restricted in capacity and throughput because of its dependency on a single connection.
- **Complexity and Resource Management:** Implementing, monitoring, and managing one link in the SC is less complicated than in the MC. MC methods, on the other hand, necessitate advanced algorithms to make decisions about packet combination, discarding, or prioritization. Also, intelligent algorithms are necessary for MC to cope with dynamically allocating resources.

It is clear from the above trade-offs that the decision between SC and MC should be based on the use cases, network demands, and compromises that best serve the objectives. However, it is worth noting that the MC is promising and required for the NTN, and more specifically for the M-SBO systems, for the following reasons:

- The inherent vast coverage of satellites boosts the availability of multi-link connectivity for UEs. By utilizing such connectivity, the MC approach may effectively mitigate some of satellite transmission's inherent flaws, such as the likelihood of connection failures due to blockage or weather conditions.
- Satellite transmission at high frequencies, such as the Ka-band, is susceptible to severe signal attenuation owing to air absorption, rain, and obstructions. Also, the necessity for macro-diversity through MC from various nodes becomes justified when shadowing becomes a serious problem.
- One of the key issues for LEO satellites is their quick motion, which results in limited service availability for UEs, frequent handover, and service interruption. As a result, MC may be a potential alternative for resolving this issue

through DC between the LEO satellites or between LEO and GEO.

Fig. 2: UE NR-DC radio protocol architecture [4].

- The integration of TN and NTN requires the use of such MC technologies to manage the combination and ensure seamless handover.
- There are several use cases proposed by the NTN that would be difficult to meet without the use of MC technology. For example, service continuity in automobiles, high-speed trains, or aircraft. Furthermore, underdeveloped areas require more bandwidth to obtain more stable and high-speed internet connectivity. This can be addressed by providing redundant links and aggregating the resources of multiple satellites or bands.

3. Potential MC Scenarios for M-SBO Systems

In what follows, we describe three potential MC scenarios and use cases along with their Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 MC scenarios and use cases for M-SBO systems.

SN.	MC Scenario	Use Case	KPI
A	Multi-band, single-GEO	Wide-area public safety	High reliability
B	Multi-band, multi-GEO	NTN-TN service continuity for mobile UE	Service continuity and high data rate
C	Single-band, multi-orbital (GEO and LEO)	Public safety system	reliability

3.1 Scenario A: Multi-band, Single GEO (Wide-Area Public Safety Use Case)

As depicted in Fig. 3, a GEO satellite with Ka and Ku bands capability offers service connectivity for emergency services across large areas. Responders equipped with UE and external

multi-band satellite antennas can stay connected via text, audio, and video even in harsh conditions. Also,

Fig. 3 Multi-band, single GEO satellite scenario.

high reliability and resilience are KPIs in emergencies where timely and accurate information transmission is critical for successful rescue and response operations. In this context, implementing SC is the relatively simple option to provide wide coverage along low modulation and coding rates to maintain a specific level of reliability. On the other hand, the MC is an appealing configuration to fulfill both high data rates and reliability. One technique to investigate is the use of inter-band CA where the user increases the bandwidth, where the UE experiences a high data rate. Also, a packet duplication scheduler could be used to improve resilience by sending copies of packets across different bands with different propagation characteristics. This may avoid possible bottlenecks or failures providing constant communication even in the face of unexpected problems, including extreme weather conditions, which may otherwise impede connection.

3.2 Scenario B: Multi-band, Multi-GEO (NTN-TN Service Continuity for Moving Vehicles Use Case)

Fig. 4 Multi-band, multi-GEO satellites scenario.

In Fig. 4, this scenario focuses on NTN-TN service continuity KPI, emphasizing the need for ubiquitous communications and coverage for connected vehicles such as cars, trains, marine, and airborne. DC plays a vital role here to connect TN and multi-GEO satellites which will allow for seamless handover and optimizes the transition between TN and multi-GEO connections. The UE may be connected to several nodes at the

same time (i.e., single GEO and TN, multi-GEO, or multi-GEO with TN). This allows for more adaptability and ensures continuous communication. When a connection is available, the UE may utilize the multi-band of GEO through CA and get a high-experience user data rate.

3.3. Scenario C: Single-Band, Multi-Orbital Satellites (GEO and LEO) for Public Safety System

The schematic diagram of this scenario is depicted in Fig. 5 and is considered the case study. It addresses the public safety connection in the absence of TN service. The integration of single-band, multi-orbital satellites including GEO with Ku band and LEO with Ka-band offers high reliability, large coverage, and extensive data rate. The utilization of the Ku band in conjunction with GEO provides wide and durable coverage over vast areas, making it perfect for seamless communication in distant locations. Also, the use of the Ka-band with LEO enables faster data speeds, meeting significant data transmission requirements.

We apply the MC by considering the DC between GEO and LEO satellites. It enables the UE to establish connections with both satellites concurrently and take advantage of the respective benefits offered by these distinct orbital configurations. Moreover, DC in this case put the GEO as an MN and LEO as an SN. This is similar to the macro/small cell arrangement in that it uses the GEO satellites' broad and steady coverage (as a macro-cell) to control and coordinate with the

more adaptable and numerous LEO satellites (as small cells). Accordingly, the GEO which has a fixed location works as an MN handling the control signaling in addition to the process of SN addition and release between the LEO satellites. This arrangement is a promising solution for the limited LEO availability and offers seamless handover between different SNs (i.e., LEO satellites). Furthermore, a packet duplication scheduler is applied where the same packet is transmitted from both satellites to improve reliability, particularly in adverse weather conditions.

In addition, we consider the regenerative satellites with CU/DU split option 1 [23, 24]. Option 1 is beneficial in the case of single-band, multi-orbital satellites. It places most of the functions in the DU which supports the interoperability between GEO and LEO satellites. It also facilitates that a single Satellite Radio Interface (SRI) is placed between the ground and the GEO satellite, whereas the Inter-Satellite Link (ISL) SRI is placed between satellites carrying the Xn interface for the MN and SN.

Furthermore, split option 2 will be equally valid in this case with the PDCP layer implemented at the on-ground CU. However, split option 2 would require an independent SRI transporting the Xn interface from the on-ground CU to the LEO DU through the GEO DU, contrarily to the split option 1 case, where the SRI connecting the GEO and LEO satellites is dedicated to the Xn interface.

Fig. 5 Single-band multi-orbital satellite scenario.

4. Numerical Results

In what follows, we consider scenario C discussed above as a case study and compare the SC and MC based on a link-level simulation focused on the Outage Probability (OP). It signifies the probability that the received signal strength (i.e., Signal-to-Noise ratio (SNR)) dropped below a predefined threshold. There are two cases of SC mode when the UE receives solely signal from the GEO or LEO. Considering the DC and the packets are duplicated and transmitted through both satellites, the OP occurs when both MN and SN are simultaneously in an outage. Table 2 shows the parameters applied and used according to the link budget analysis in [2, 25].

Table 2: System parameters for DC between GEO and LEO.

Parameter	MN (GEO)	SN (LEO)
Altitude (Km)	35,786	600
Frequency [GHz]	12	20
Bandwidth [MHz]	36	400
Maximum EIRP [dBW]	49.4	36
Receive antenna-gain-to-noise-temperature [dB/K]	19.6	15.9
Elevation angle	90°	30°
Fading	Shadow Rician	

Fig. 6 contrasts the OP for different SNR threshold (ϵ) values in SC and DC under standard weather conditions (i.e., no rain attenuation). The results show that the DC steadily outperforms both SC modes from LEO and GEO, particularly at $\epsilon < 17$ dB. The DC curve increases slowly with increasing SNR, which indicates that the system can tolerate higher SNR values without going to an outage. One can also observe that the LEO reaches outage faster than GEO mainly due to its lower elevation angle. Given that this angle is always changing owing to the satellite's motion, it emphasizes the need to use DC to strengthen the LEO link and solve its limitation. Furthermore, the higher advantage of applying packet duplication with DC is noticed in Fig. 7, for the case of adverse weather conditions (i.e., rain attenuation is equal to 10 dB). The OP is achieved at $\epsilon = 20$ dB in the case of DC compared to $\epsilon = 8$ dB for the case of SC from the LEO satellite. This demonstrates the importance of DC to ensure service availability and link reliability when the LEO link is in an outage. The GEO with Ku band having different propagation characteristics than LEO increases the probability of successive reception of the transmitted packets. Hence, it is important to emphasize recognizing these performance differences may have a direct impact on satellite communication tactics, resulting in more robust and resilient communication channels. Furthermore, as satellite technology

advances, the significance of DC in improving connection performance in a variety of atmospheric situations becomes increasingly important.

5. Conclusion

This study investigates downlink multi-satellite connectivity solutions in 6G communication networks, focusing on Single-Connectivity (SC) and Multi-Connectivity (MC) perspectives, technologies (i.e., Carrier Aggregation (CA) and Dual Connectivity (DC)), scenarios, and trade-offs. DC between GEO and LEO for public safety communication terminals has highlighted the advantages of employing such a configuration to improve reliability sustain the LEO connection and address its limited availability. Key results highlight the features of MC technologies. For instance, applying DC between GEO and LEO with packet duplication may greatly improve downlink reliability, particularly under poor weather circumstances. Future work will further examine other KPIs in addition to the influence of different CU/DU split functions on the performance of MC techniques. More MC potential scenarios will be also investigated.

Fig. 6 OP comparison between SC and MC in normal weather conditions.

Fig. 7 OP comparison between SC and MC in adverse weather conditions.

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